

AXBOROTLASHGAN JAMIYAT, UNING MAZMUN MOHIYATI VA TARIXAN RIVOJLANISHI

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Abstract. XXI asr insoniyat tarixiga yangi axborot asri nomi bilan kirib keldi. Bugungi davr shiddat bilan rivojlanib borayotgan axborot texnologiyalari, kibernetika, kompyuter va boshqa nano texnologiyalarning rivoji bilan xarakterlanadi. Maqolada Axborot, axborotlashgan jamiyat tushunchasining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi, kelib chiqish sabablari, mazmun-mohiyati haqida gap boradi. Shuningdek ushbu maqolada axborotlashgan jamiyat tushunchasining kelib chiqishiga tegishli boʻlgan tarixiy faktlar, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sabablar haqida va bugungi kundagi jarayonlarni qamrab oladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Axborotlashuv, axborotlashgan jamiyat, integratsiya, globalizatsiya, kompleks axloq, ijtimoiy aloqa, axloqiy norma, madaniy meʼyor, internet, kompyuter, elektronika, kibernetika, yangi davr sohalari, qadimgi davr sivilizatsiyalari, XXI asr demokratiyasi, sotsiologik taʼsir, etnogenez, yagona qadiryat, qonun, chegara, erkinlik, vijdon.

INFORMATION SOCIETY, ITS CONTENT NATURE AND HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT

Abstract. The 21st century entered the history of humanity under the name of a new information age. Today's era is characterized by the development of rapidly developing information technologies, cybernetics, computers and other nano technologies. The article talks about the historical evolution of the concept of information, information society, its origins, and its essence. Also, this article covers historical facts, socio-economic reasons and current processes related to the origin of the concept of information society.

Key words: Information communication, information society, integration, globalization, complex ethics, social communication, moral norm, cultural norm, internet, computer, electronics, cybernetics, new age fields, ancient civilizations, 21st century democracy, sociological influence, ethnogenesis, single power, law, limit, freedom, conscience.

ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЕ ОБЩЕСТВО, ЕГО СОДЕРЖАНИЕ, ПРИРОДА И ИСТОРИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ

Аннотация. XXI век вошел в историю человечества под названием нового информационного века. Сегодняшняя эпоха характеризуется развитием быстро развивающихся информационных технологий, кибернетики, компьютеров и других нанотехнологий. В статье говорится об исторической эволюции понятия информации, информационного общества, его истоках и сущности. Также в данной статье рассматриваются исторические факты, социально-экономические причины и современные процессы, связанные с зарождением концепции информационного общества.

Ключевые слова: Информационная коммуникация, информационное общество, интеграция, глобализация, сложная этика, социальная коммуникация, моральная норма, культурная норма, интернет, компьютер, электроника, кибернетика, поля нового века,

древние цивилизации, демократия XXI века, социологическое влияние, этногенез, единая власть, право, предел, свобода, совесть.

XXI asr insoniyat tarixiga yangi axborot asri nomi bilan kirib keldi. Bugungi davr shiddat bilan rivojlanib borayotgan axborot texnologiyalari, kibernetika, kompyuter va boshqa nano texnologiyalarning rivoji bilan xarakterlanadi.

Axborotlashgan jamiyat atamasi o'tgan asrning 60-70 yillaridan Yapon va Amerikada qo'llanila boshlagan. Asosan axborotni olish, saqlash, yig'ish, uzatish imkoni yuqori bo'lgan, rivojlangan axborot texnologiyalari, kommunikatsiyasialari, axborot infratuzilmalariga ega jamiyatlarga nisbatan "Axborotlashgan jamiyat" tushunchasi qo'llaniladi. Bu tushunchaning aniq bir gnesiologik, empirik va falsafiy muqobil ta'rifi yo'q. Uning kelib chiqishiga oid turli xil qarashlar mavjud masalan "Axborotlashgan jamiyatning" kelib chiqishi sanoat inqilobi davriga to'g'ri keladi bu davrda ishlab chiqaruv avtomatlashtirilgan, uzoqqa tashish imkoniyati mavjud bo'lgan, zamonaviylashgan tizimlar tendensiyalar nazorat qilish aloqa o'rnatish, masofadan boshqarishni taqazo etgani bilan bog'liq deb hisoblaydi.

Steinfeld va Salvaggio axborotlashgan jamiyatni 5 ta yo'nalishga bo'ladi bular: Iqtisodiy (ishlab chiqarish), iste'mol, texnologik, tanqidiy va ko'p o'lchovli.

Faylasuf P.Ф. Абдеев fikricha Axborot hodisasini tushuntirishda ikki xil bahsmunozaralar mavjud bo'lgan. Axborotning atributiv va funksional tushunchalari bir-biriga qarama-qarshidir. "Atributistlar" axborotni barcha moddiy obyektlarga xos xususiyat, materiyaning atributi sifatida kvalifikatsiya qiladi. "Funksionalistlar" esa, aksincha, axborotni hayotning paydo bo'lishi bilangina paydo bo'lgan deb hisoblab, o'z-o'zini tashkil etuvchi tizimlar faoliyati bilan bog'laydilar.

Axborotlashgan jamiyat tushunchasini izohlashga bo'lgan ta'riflar oxirgi 30-yil mobaynida turli xil shakillarni oldi. Ko'pgina faylasuf-olimlar, tarixchilar tarixdan to bugunga qadar bo'lgan insoniyat rivojlanish bosqich dinamikasini (svilizatsiyani) uch bosqichga bo'lishgan bular; agrar svilizatsiya, postindustrial svilizatsiya va industrial svilizatsiya. Bugungi axborotlashgan jamiyatga – to'rtinchi to'liqin yoki to'rtinchi svilizatsiya sifatida qaralmoqda. XXI asr – globallashuv davri, texnika asri. Global tarzda texnologiyalar va aloqa kommunikatsiyalari rivojlanib, taraqqiy etib borishi o'ziga xos ravishda iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, madaniy holatlarni keltirib chiqarmoqda. Globallashuv davrida jamiyatlar shiddat bilan integratsiyalashmoqda. Bu integratsiyalashuv jamiyatdagi insonlarning induvdal va umumiy tarzda global ijtimoiy aloqalar olib borish imkoniyatlarini favqulotda tezlashtirib yubordi. Yangi davrdagi o'zaro ijtimoiy aloqalar asta-sekinlik bilan barcha uchun bir xil axloq, madaniyat qoidalariga undovchi kompleks axloq ya'ni ommaviy madaniyatni keng yoyilishiga sabab bo'lib yangicha "XXI asr demokratiyasi" nomini olmoqda. Buning salbiy tomonlaridan biri shundaki - aynan bir jamiyat uchun xos bo'lgan milliy, hududiy va tarixiy shakillangan - axloqiy, madaniy me'yor chegaralarining o'rnini turli xil jamiyatlarning axloqiy, madaniy, sotsiologik ta'sir qorishmalaridan iborat bo'lgan globall axloq va madaniyat egallamoqda. Axloqiy meyor qoidalari va madaniyat chegaralari har qachongi davrdan ko'ra ahamiyati yuqoriroqdir. Buguni kunda burch, mas'uliyat, vijdon, axloqiy norma barcha jamiyatlarda xususan biz uchun ham dolzarb masaladir.

Faylasuf olimi L.A.Muhammedjanovning fikricha: - “Bugun dunyo chuqur o‘zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda. Iqtisodiy o‘zaro globallashtirish va kuchayib borayotgan o‘zaro bog‘liqlik, kuchli va hamma joyda mavjud aholi migratsiyasi. Ijtimoiy tuzilmadagi o‘zgarishlar chuqurlashib, jamiyatlar tez rivojlanmoqda. Bunday holatlar sodir bo‘lganda murakkab o‘zgarishlar, millatlararo nizolarga olib kelishi mumkin, dunyoning turli burchaklarida to‘qnashuvlar hali ham rivojlanmoqda. Jamiyat borlig‘idagi - milliy, etnik, millatlararo munosabatlar, muammolar, vazifalar ularning yechimi, o‘tmishda ishlatilgan eski vositalar va usullar bilan hal etilmay qoldi. Hayot kun tartibiga yangi muammolarni qo‘ydi-milliy masalaga yondashish va eski usullardan qat‘iy voz kechish.”

Bugungi davr jamiyatlar o‘zaro faol integratsiyalashayotgan, axborot texnikasi, kommunikatsiya, texnologiyalar rivoji globallashtirayotgan bir so‘z bilan aytganda globallashtirish va axborotlashayotgan jamiyatlar qaror topayotgan davrdir. Axborotlashgan jamiyatning qaror topishi tezlashayotgan davrda uni har tomonlama o‘rganishimiz biz uchun tobora hayotiy zaruratga aylanib bormoqda va bunday jamiyat kelib chiqish tarixi, sabablarini o‘rganishimiz ham kun tartibidagi asosiy masalardan biridir zero bugungi kunda biz ham shu jamiyat tomon asta-sekin yuzlanmoqdamiz.

Insoniyat paydo bo‘lgan davrdan boshlab to bugungi asrga qadar turli xil rivojlanish yo‘llarini bosib o‘tib sivilizatsiya nomini oldi. Rivojlanish davrining eng ibtidoiy davridan hozirgi rivojlangan davrigacha axborot insoniyatning regulyativ vazifasini belgilab berishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etdi. Axborot insonning gnesiologik-ratsional, irratsional bilimlarning asosini tashkil qiladi. Axborot qadimdan isonlarning tur sifatida yashab qolishiga va keyingi revolyutsiyasida muhim ahamiyat kasb etgan. Dastlabgi axborot shakli inuitiv tarzda rivojlangan ya‘ni o‘zini saqlab qolishga intilish shaklida, keyinchalik insonlarda yig‘ilgan axborotlar jamlanib nutq ko‘rinishini olgan bu insonlar orasidagi eng dastlabgi buyuk integrativ va aloqa shakli hisoblanib, insoniyat tarixidagi dastlabki ongli muloqot davrini boshlab bergan. Insoniyat ongining muhim xususiyati shundaki, u axborotlarni ya‘ni informatsiyalarni saqlash, qayta ishlash, uzatish, berilgan axborotlar asosida ong ma‘lumotlarni ya‘ni o‘z-o‘zini qayta ishlash va o‘zgartirish xususiyatiga ega. Insonlarda muloqot paydo bo‘lishi axborotning og‘zaki shaklini vujudga keltirdi. Insonlarning tevarak olamni teranroq tushunishga intilishi rasmlar va shakillar yaratilishiga, bu esa ma‘lum ma‘nolarni ifodalovchi iyegroflarni ya‘ni “fikr axborotini” shakillantirdi iyegroflar yozuvlarni yaratilishiga olib keldi, rivojlanish asosan axborotlarning to‘planishi tufayli sodir bo‘ldi. Yozuvning kashf etilishi axborotning muloqot shakli bilan birgalikda yozma shaklini ham vujudga keltirdi. Yozuv axborotning funksiyalari taraqqiyotini tezlashtirib insonlar o‘rtasidagi aloqani yangi bosqichga kotardi va bu fan, estetik, etik, ratsional bilimlarning qaror topishiga, jamiyatlarning taraqqiylashuvi muhim turtki berdi. Yozuvning nutq axborotidan farqli jihati makon [masofa] va zamon [vaqt] nuqtayi nazaridan cheklanmaganligida. Yozuv axboroti axborotning shu paytgacha bo‘lgan funksiyalari, vazifalariga yangicha yo‘nalish va takomillashtirish olib kirdi shuningdek davlat boshqaruvi funksiyalarini murakkab, kengroq ko‘lamga olib chiqdi. Masalan dastlabki yozuvlar yaqin sharqda old Osiyoda [Finikiya aifbosi] vujudga kelgan bo‘lsa aynan shu hududlarda dastlabki Jamiyat a‘zolari uchun bajarilishi va bilishi shart hisoblangan yozma axborot – Qonun ishlab chiqildi [Xamurapi qonunlari – Bobil Old Osiyo] va amalda jamiyat ustidan nazorat qilish, boshqarish uyun qo‘llanildi. Insoniyat taraqqiyotida ilk

fanlar tasnifini vujudga kelishi, rivojlanishi (xususan Qadimgi Yunonistonda – Antik davr) - axborotning insonlarga beradigan vazifa, mazmuniga ham jiddiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi, ma'lum vaqtlardan so'ng dastabgi fanlar vujudga kelib bu fanlar zarur bo'lgan axborotlardan foydalanish uchun dasturamal vazifasini bajargan. Insonlar yozuvdan foydalanishni boshlagandan so'ng dastab qo'lyozma, tarixiy yilnoma, shunga o'xshash bitiklar va eng muhimi dastlabgi yozma axborot – kitobdan foydalanishga boshlanib bu insoniyatning ong va bilim darajasini yuqori bosqichga olib chiqdi.

Avvallari axborot birlik ya'ni tor ma'noda asosan ma'lumot olish-berish shaklida bo'lgan bo'lsa endilikda axborot kengroq insonda falsafiy, axloqiy-estetik, boshqaruv, iqtisod va boshqa bilimlarni rivojlanishiga qaratildi. Dastlab kitoblardan chegaralangan darajada foydalanilgan, o'rta asrlar davriga kelib 1445-yilda Ioan Gutenberg kitob bosish dastgohini kashf etishi bilan bu jarayon insonlarni qamrab olish darajasini yuqori darajada oshirdi. Kitob bosish dastgohini ixtiro etilishi zamonaviy yozma axborot tizimlarining chinakam asosi bolmish matbuotning paydo bo'lishiga sababchi bo'ldi. Aloqa voitalari, radio, televideniya, zamonaviy texnologiyalar paydo bo'lgunga qadar matbuot asosiy axborot tarqatuvchi vazifasini bajardi. Axborotga bo'lgan kuchli ehtiyojning vujudga kelishi XV-XVI asrlarda yangi bilimlarning, dunyoqarashning vujudga kelishi shuningdek Buyuk geografik kashfiyotlar omili sifatida ko'riladi. Aynan shu davr bugungi axborot turlariga shakil, mazmun-mohiyatan negiz hisoblanadi. Keyingi davrlarda axborotning asosiy manbasi yozma axborot vositalari hisoblangan bo'lsa, ilm-fan yutuqlari, yangi texnologiyalar kashf etilishi, yangicha dunyoqarash, insonlarning asta-sekin globall kommunikativ va integratsion aloqalarga, agrar jamiyatdan - industrial jamiyatga bo'lgan qadam yangicha axborot texnologiyalariga bo'lgan ehtiyojni ortirdi, natijada dastlab radio keyinchalik esa televideniya-telekommunikatsiyalar yaratilishiga olib keldi. Televideniya insonlarning eng muhim va ommabob axborot vositasiga aylandi. Telekomunikatsiya, aniq fanlar, EHM, kibernetika sohalarining taraqqiyoti axborotning global tarzda ommalashuvi, rivojlanishini osonlashtirdi. Bu sohalarning taraqqiyoti asosan G'arbiy yevropa davlatlarida ertaroq kechdi sababi bu davlatlarning iqtisodiy taraqqiyoti, ilmiy muhit va liberal munosabatlarning boshqa mintaqalardan avvalroq qaror topgani. Keyingi davrlarda davlat va jamiyatlar taraqqiyoti uning axborot resurslari bilan qanchalik ta'minlanganligiga qarab belgilanib-axborotlashgan jamiyat tushunchasi qo'llanila boshlandi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni ta'kidlash mumkinki butun dunyoda AKT texnologiyalari, raqamli iqtisodiyoti, avtomatlashtirish rivoji, umumiy axborot texnologiyalari taraqqiyoti kishilik jamiyatini yangi bosqichga olib chiqmoqda. Tarix shuni ko'rsatadiki har bir kishilik jamiyati yangi bosqichga o'tilishi evolutsion, tadrijiy yo'sinda amalga oshadi. Har bir yangi bosqichda yangi kasblar, yangi odatlar, yangicha san'at, fan, madaniyat, siyosat, maorif, axloq, yangicha dunyoqarash vujudga keladi. Axborotlashgan jamiyatga o'tishni bugungi kunda ayrim davlatlar davlat dasturi darajasiga ham kirgizishmoqda. Bu jamiyatga qadam tashlash ko'pgina sohalarda sifat va miqdor jihatdan ustunlikni ta'minlashga yordam beradi. Yuqorida aytib o'tganimizdek axborotlashgan jamiyat ko'pgina sohalarga inovatsion taraqqiyot bag'ishlaydi xususan insonlarning ijtimoiy, madaniy hayotiga ham. Jumladan bizning yurtimizda ham insonlarni oliy o'quv yurtiga qamrab olish, ta'lim tizimini raqamlashtirish, inovatsion ta'lim muassasalarini tashkillashtirish, fuqarolar erkinligi va huquiy ongini yuksaltirish, erkinlik, ochiqlik, va

oshkoralik, fuqarolarni davlat boshqaruvida yalpi ishtirok etishini ta'minlashda axborot texnologiyalarining o'rni beqiyosdir. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash joizki butun dunyoda ketayotgan chuqur iqtisodiy - ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar insonlar uchun axloq va madaniyatning ahamiyatlilik darajasini yuqori darajaga olib chiqmoqda zero axloq – bu tarixning ruhidir. Oljayevna, O., & Shavkatovna, S. (2020). The Development of Logical Thinking of Primary School Students in Mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences*, 8(2), 235-239.

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